

Yes, I consent to participate in this research.

No, I do not consent.

Self-Perceived Experience

Before continuing, we need to verify your eligibility. Please answer the following questions about small programming snippets.

Throughout this study, you may use documentation to clarify the behavior of functions used within snippets. We ask only that you **do not execute the snippets you see**.

Do you consider yourself experienced with the Java programming language?

In other words, you understand the syntax and function of the language, and would be able to design moderately-sized projects in the language, allowing for the consultation of documentation and other resources.

Very experienced

Somewhat experienced

Not experienced

Do you consider yourself experienced with the Python programming language (either Python 2 or 3)?

Very experienced

Somewhat experienced

Not experienced

What will this function return when the input is the integer 6?

```
1 public static int ANON_FUNC(int input) {
2     int sum = 0;
3
4     for (int i = 1; i < input; i+=2) {
5         sum += i;
6     }
7
8     return sum;
9 }
```

True or false: for a given list of integers, this function returns the first integer that appears **more than once**, or None if none do.

```
1 def ANON_FUNC(intarr):
2     for number in intarr:
3         if intarr.count(number) == 1:
4             return number
5     return None
```

- True
- False

What will this function return when the input is the string "codeclone"?

```
1 public static String ANON_FUNC(String input) {
2     int length = input.length();
3     int middle = length / 2;
4     return length % 2 == 0 ?
5         input.substring(middle - 1, middle + 1) :
6         String.valueOf(input.charAt(middle));
7 }
```

- c
- ec
- e
- cl
- The function will not compile or run.

What does this function return when the input is the string "racecar"?

```
1 def ANON_FUNC(val):
2     for x, y in zip(val, val[::-1]):
3         if x != y:
4             return False
5     return True
```

- True
- False
- The function will not run.

Code Clones Explanation

Congratulations! You have passed the qualifying questions and are ready to start the survey.

In this survey, we are investigating types of **behavioral code clones**, which are programs that give the same output for all of a given range of inputs, even if they don't follow the same algorithm.

These clones may look very similar or very different, but it is their behavior—how they respond for given input—that matters.

For example, the snippets below are written differently, but all of them return the sum of an array or list of integers.

```
1 public int sum1(int[] arr) {
2     int accum = 0;
3     for (int i = 0; i < arr.length; ++i) {
4         accum += arr[i];
5     }
6     return accum;
7 }
8
9
10 public int ANON_FUNC(int[] arr) {
11     int acc = 0, index = 0;
12     while (index < arr.length) {
13         acc += arr[index];
14         ++index;
15     }
16     return acc;
17 }
18
19
20 public int sumstream(int[] arr) {
21     return Arrays.stream(arr).sum();
22 }
```

pyfile.py

```
1 def sumpy(intarr):
2     return sum(intarr)
3
```

Java and Python do have different language rules for determining the maximum sizes of arrays or integers, but as long as we define an expected domain of input—up to a million integers in $[-1,000,000, 1,000,000]$ —then we can be more confident that they are clones.

However, looks can be deceiving. Code snippets may look nearly identical but accomplish different tasks.

```
1 public int sum1(int[] arr) {
2     int accum = 0;
3     for (int i = 0; i < arr.length; ++i) {
4         accum += arr[i];
5     }
6     return accum;
7 }
8
9
10 public int maybesum(int[] arr) {
11     int accum = 0;
12     for (int i = 0; i < arr.length; ++i) {
13         accum *= arr[i];
14     }
15     return accum;
16 }
```

These functions differ only by 1 character within the for-loop: + in line 4 of the first becomes * in the second. However, this character transforms the result of the function. Therefore, although they could be considered near clones **by syntax**, they are not clones **by behavior**.

Skill Assessment

Here are a few sample questions to demonstrate what to expect. They will not count to your overall response.

For each question, we will define the domain of expected inputs for the function. You do not have to consider any behavioral differences between the functions that occurs outside the expected inputs unless otherwise prompted.

Are the two Python snippets below behavioral clones? That is, do they return the same output for every valid input?

Valid input: a string up to 100 characters, consisting of alphanumeric characters (A-Z and 0-9) and spaces.

```
1 def ANON_FUNC_1(val):
2     for x, y in zip(val, val[::-1]):
3         if x != y:
4             return False
5     return True
```

```
1 def ANON_FUNC_2(val):
2     for i in range(len(val)):
3         if val[i] != val[-i]:
4             return False
5     return True
```

- Yes, they are clones
- No, they are not clones
- There is not enough information to tell.

Although both iterate across a string from both ends, when $i=0$, the second function begins by comparing the characters at 0 and -0, which is the first character for both. The first snippet will start by comparing the first with the last character. As such, while the first snippet detects palindromes, the second does not.

An input that demonstrates it is "aaba"; the first function returns False but the second returns True.

Correct! Although both iterate across a string from both ends, when $i=0$, the second function begins by comparing the characters at 0 and -0, which is the first character for both. The first snippet will start by comparing the first with the last character. As such, while the first snippet detects palindromes, the second does not.

An input that demonstrates it is "aaba"; the first function returns False but the second returns True.

Are the two snippets below behavioral clones? That is, do they return the same output for every valid input?

Valid input: a string up to 100 characters, consisting of sequences of up to 8 numeric characters (1-9) separated by single spaces.

```
1 def ANON_FUNC(var):
2     return sum(int(x) for x
3                 in var.split(" "))
4
5
6
7
8

1 public int addString(String str) {
2     String[] parts = str.split(" ");
3     int sum = 0;
4     for (String part : parts) {
5         sum += Integer.parseInt(part);
6     }
7     return sum;
8 }
```

- Yes, they are clones
- No, they are not clones
- There is not enough information to tell.

Correct! The two snippets are in different languages with different syntax, but each one splits, parses, and sums up the input for the same result.

The input specification is important, however. Java would not be able to parse indefinitely long strings of numeric characters, up to the maximum value of the int type.

They are clones. The two snippets are in different languages with different syntax, but each one splits, parses, and sums up the input for the same result.

The input specification is important, however. Java would not be able to parse indefinitely long strings of numeric characters, up to the maximum value of the int type.

Task Explanation

You will now proceed to the main survey. Due to the nature of the study, you will not be able to return to questions once you have submitted an answer.

- There will be 5 tasks. For each task, you will be given two snippets and an input domain. Select whether the snippets are behavioral clones---that is, whether they will return the same thing for **all** of the same input within the domain.

- Python snippets should be valid in current versions of either Python 2 or 3, and Python lists are used interchangeably as arrays.
- If you are uncertain of what a function or programming construct in one of the questions does, you may consult documentation. **However, we ask that you do not recreate and run the snippets in your own environments.**

Task 1

Valid input: a nonempty array of up to a million base-10 integers between -1,000,000,000 and +1,000,000,000.

Example inputs:

[1]

[9, 88, 777, 6666, 55555, 444444, 3333333, 22222222, 111111111]

[-1000000, 50, 0, 0, 0, -50, 1000000]

For the given input domain, are the snippets behavioral clones?

- Yes
- No
- I'm missing the following important information:

- I don't know.

Considering all possible inputs of the relevant types (and not the limited domain we provided), are the snippets behavioral clones?

- Yes
- No
- I'm missing the following important information:

I don't know.

What is an input or the type of input for which the snippets return different values?

Thinking about how you arrived at your answer, which characteristics of the snippets do you think were the strongest clues for whether they were clones or not?

- Function and variable names
- Shape or length of the code
- Control flow (e.g. conditionals, loops)
- Data flow (e.g. uses and destinations of input)
- Something else

None of the above

Task 2

Valid input: a string of at most 100 characters, consisting of alphanumeric characters (A-Z and 0-9) and underscores.

Example inputs:

"sample_input"

"_abc_def_"

"1_two_3_four_5_six_7_eight_9_ten"

For the given input domain, are the snippets behavioral clones?

- Yes
- No
- Cannot be answered without the following information:

I don't know.

Considering all possible inputs of the relevant types (and not the limited domain we provided), are the snippets behavioral clones?

Yes

No

Cannot be answered without the following information:

I don't know

What is an input or type of input for which the snippets return different values?

Thinking about how you arrived at your answer, which characteristics of the snippets do you think were the strongest clues for whether they were clones or not?

Function and variable names

Shape or length of the code

Control flow (e.g. conditionals, loops)

Data flow (e.g. uses and destinations of input)

Something else

None of the above

Task 3

Valid input: Two strings of at most 100 characters, comprising alphanumeric characters (A-Z and 0-9), punctuation, and whitespace.

Example inputs:

"one", "two"

"first argument", "second argument"
"", "1,000,000 arguments, with a cup of tea"

For the given input domain, are the snippets behavioral clones?

- Yes
- No
- Cannot be answered without the following information:

- I don't know

Considering all possible inputs of the relevant types (and not the limited domain we provided), are the snippets behavioral clones?

- Yes
- No
- Cannot be answered without the following information:

- I don't know.

What is an input or type of input for which the snippets return different values?

Thinking about how you arrived at your answer, which characteristics of the snippets do you think were the strongest clues for whether they were clones or not?

- Function and variable names
- Shape or length of the code
- Control flow (e.g. conditionals, loops)
- Data flow (e.g. uses and destinations of input)

Something else

None of the above

Task 4

Valid input: two strings of at most 100 characters, consisting of only alphanumeric characters (A-Z and 0-9) and spaces.

Example inputs:

"one", "two"

"first argument", "2nd argument"

"196552", "519256"

For the given input domain, are the snippets behavioral clones?

Yes

No

Cannot be answered without the following information:

I don't know

Considering all possible inputs of the relevant types (and not the limited domain we provided), are the snippets behavioral clones?

Yes

No

Cannot be answered without the following information:

I don't know

Considering all possible inputs of the relevant types (and not the limited domain we provided), are the snippets behavioral clones?

- Yes
- No
- Cannot be answered without the following information:

- I don't know

What is an input or type of input for which the snippets return different values?

Thinking about how you arrived at your answer, which characteristics of the snippets do you think were the strongest clues for whether they were clones or not?

- Function and variable names
- Shape or length of the code
- Control flow (e.g. conditionals, loops)
- Data flow (e.g. uses and destinations of input)
- Something else

- None of the above

Task 9

Input: a string of at most 100 characters, comprising alphanumeric characters (A-Z and 0-9), punctuation, underscores, and whitespace.

Example input:

"programming"

"abc_123"

"veering too far, I gripped the wheel"

For the given input domain, are the snippets behavioral clones?

- Yes
- No
- Cannot be answered without the following information:

- I don't know

Considering all possible inputs of the relevant types (and not the limited domain we provided), are the snippets behavioral clones?

- Yes
- No
- Cannot be answered without the following information:

- I don't know

What is an input or type of input for which the snippets return different values?

Thinking about how you arrived at your answer, which characteristics of the snippets do you think were the strongest clues for whether they were clones or not?

- Function and variable names
- Shape or length of the code
- Control flow (e.g. conditionals, loops)
- Data flow (e.g. uses and destinations of input)

Something else

None of the above

Task 10

Input: a string of at most 100 alphanumeric (A-Z and 0-9) and whitespace characters, and a positive integer up to 100.

Example input:

"to go is a bad way", 3

"middled", 20

"one two three four five six seven eight nine ten eleven twelve", 12

For the given input domain, are the snippets behavioral clones?

Yes

No

Cannot be answered without the following information:

I don't know

Considering all possible inputs of the relevant types (and not the limited domain we provided), are the snippets behavioral clones?

Yes

No

Cannot be answered without the following information:

I don't know

What is an input or type of input for which the snippets return different values?

Thinking about how you arrived at your answer, which characteristics of the snippets do you think were the strongest clues for whether they were clones or not?

- Function and variable names
- Shape or length of the code
- Control flow (e.g. conditionals, loops)
- Data flow (e.g. uses and destinations of input)
- Something else

- None of the above

Two more?

Do you have time for two more tasks, or do you want to proceed to the end of the survey?

- I want to take 2 more tasks.
- I want to go to the end of the survey.

Professional History & Demography

During any of the tasks, did you execute any of the snippets or excerpts presented to you?
This answer will have no bearing eligibility and compensation.

- Yes, I ran one or more full snippets.
- Yes, I ran individual lines or statements from a snippet.
- No, I executed no code.

Thinking about how you arrived at your answers, which characteristics of the snippets do you think are the most helpful clues overall about whether two snippets were behavioral clones?

Extremely important Very important Moderately important Slightly important Not at all important

	Extremely important	Very important	Moderately important	Slightly important	Not at all important
Function and variable names	<input type="radio"/>				
Shape or length of the code	<input type="radio"/>				
Control flow	<input type="radio"/>				
Data flow	<input type="radio"/>				

What characteristic do you look for first?

- Function and variable names
- Shape or length of the code
- Control flow
- Data flow
- Something else
- Nothing consistently; it depends.

Is there any other supplemental information you would like to see provided with snippets that would help you distinguish them? This could be static analysis, comparison of dynamic information, or more.

(Optional) How would you describe your overall strategy for comparing code snippets in this study?

(Optional) Do you have any feedback about the survey or experiment itself? For example, were any of the instructions unclear?

Thank you for your response. To wrap things up, we will now gather any demographic information you feel comfortable sharing. This will help us understand the context of your responses.

How frequently do you search for code snippets online, on average?

- Once a workday
- A few times a workday
- Once a week
- A few times weekly
- Once a month
- A few times monthly
- Less than monthly
- Prefer not to say

Thinking of your work in the past month, where have you searched for specific elements or examples of code? Text-entry boxes are for specifying a particular instance of a type of location.

- Personal code projects
- Company code projects
- Google
- Code Search Engines (e.g. Krugle)
- GitHub
- Other repository systems (e.g. SourceForge):
- Stack Overflow or Stack Exchange
- Other Q&A websites:
- Software tutorials and blogs:
- Other
- None
- Prefer not to say

Other than correct or near-correct behavior, what are the most important qualities of a good reusable code snippet?

How old are you?

- 18 - 24
- 25 - 34
- 35 - 44
- 45 - 54
- 55 - 64
- 65 - 74
- 75 - 84
- 85 or older
- Prefer not to say

How many years of experience do you have with software development?

- Less than 2 years
- 2 to <5 years
- 5 to <10 years
- 10 to <20 years
- More than 20 years
- Prefer not to say

What is the highest degree you hold from formal education?

- High school, GED, or less
- Some college but no degree
- Vocational or trade training
- Associate's or 2-year degree
- Bachelor's or 4-year degree
- Professional degree
- Master's degree
- Doctorate degree
- Prefer not to say

Do you have a degree in computer science, software engineering, or another field in which programming is central to the curriculum?

- Yes
- No

Prefer not to say

What best describes your current primary occupation?

- Undergraduate student
- Graduate student
- Academic researcher or educator
- Professionally employed in the software industry
- Professionally employed outside the software industry
- Self-employed
- Not currently employed
- Other
- Prefer not to say

In your professional history, have you ever been employed as a software developer or within a software development team?

- Yes
- No
- Prefer not to say

With which gender do you identify?

- Male
- Female
- Nonbinary
- Prefer to self-identify (optional fill-in):
- Prefer not to say

For compensation purposes, did you apply to this survey through Mechanical Turk?

- Yes, I am here through Mechanical Turk
- No, I applied through a link or a different website.

MTurk Compensation

Thank you for completing the survey! Now we can collect the information necessary to compensate you while keeping your survey data anonymous.

Please enter your Mechanical Turk worker ID (to ensure proper task verification and compensation).

Please enter the following number in the Mechanical Turk survey submission form: $\{e://Field/CompensationID\}$

Other Compensation

Thank you for completing the survey! In order to receive compensation, we will direct you to a separate survey. This way, we can collect the information necessary to compensate you while keeping your survey data anonymous.